

DIPG cases from HULAFE's Paediatric Cancer Collection

ID: 91411e6c-a550-4825-ab01-5497e4c49826

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Studies count: 55

Subjects count: 21

Age range: Between 2 years and 13 years

Sex: Male, Female

Body part(s): HEAD, CSPINE, Unknown

Modality: MR, CT